

AKI ASSOCIATED WITH COVID-19, MOST AFFECTED AGE GROUP, COMORBIDITIES, AND MORTALITY

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Abstract

COVID-19 is an infectious disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus that emerged in late 2019. The disease rapidly spread from its origin in Wuhan, China, and has since become an unprecedented global pandemic. Its impact on the world's population has been catastrophic, resulting in over six million deaths worldwide, making it the most significant global health crisis since the 1918 flu pandemic. [1,2,3]

Keywords: AKI, COVID-19, pandemic, comorbidities

Introduction

While COVID-19 primarily affects the respiratory system, it can also have deleterious effects on the kidneys. Severe cases of COVID-19 have been associated with elevated serum creatinine and serum urea levels, hematuria, proteinuria, and AKI, all of which are linked to a higher mortality rate. Among critically ill patients with SARS-CoV2 infection, up to 25% may develop AKI, particularly those with pre-existing comorbidities such as diabetes or hypertension. The mortality rate is significantly higher in patients who require renal replacement therapy for AKI. [4,5]

Aim of the study

Considering the substantial number of patients who developed AKI during hospitalization for COVID-19, our objective is to investigate the most prevalent comorbidities associated with a heightened risk of AKI development. Additionally, we seek to compare mor-

tality rates between two patient groups: those who developed AKI unrelated to COVID-19 and those who developed AKI while infected with COVID-19.

Materials and methods

The study included a group of 66 patients with AKI diagnosis who were hospitalized in "Timofei Moşneaga" Republican Clinical Hospital during the first semester of 2021. The study included 22 (33.3%) patients who had had AKI associated with COVID-19. The age of the patients varies from 37 to 84 years, and the average age is 64.1 years. AKI was diagnosed more often in men – 45 (68,2%) than in women – 21 (31,8%).

Results and discussion

From the data collected from the patient's medical records, the highest rate of AKI not associated with COVID-19 was found in the age group 61-70 years. The increased prevalence of pathology in this age group is probably due to the multiple comorbidities and weakening of the immune system in elderly people (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Age groups of patients with AKI not associated with COVID-19.

Upon examining the age distribution of patients with AKI linked to COVID-19, it was observed that the prevalence of the disease was highest in patients aged 71-80 years, with 10 patients (48%) falling within this age group. However, there was also an increase in the

prevalence of AKI in the age group of 51-60 years, with 6 patients (29%) affected. This trend suggests a rejuvenation of the pathology in association with SARS-CoV2 infection (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Age groups of patients with AKI associated with COVID-19.

The patient’s comorbidities confer an increased risk for AKI development, the most common are diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and heart failure. For this reason, we analyzed the data regarding the patient’s associated pathologies to detect the most common one. Diabetes mellitus was detected in 10 (45.5%) of the pa-

tients with AKI associated with COVID-19, arterial hypertension was present in 18 (81.8%) patients and heart failure of various etiology was attested in 15 (68.1 %) of the patients. Only two patients did not present any associated chronic pathology at the time of admission (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Comorbidities in patients with AKI associated with COVID-19.

Among patients who developed AKI not linked to COVID-19, it was observed that the most prevalent comorbidity was arterial hypertension, present in 28 patients (63.6%). The second most common comorbidity

was heart failure, identified in 27 patients (61.3%), followed by diabetes mellitus, which was present in 15 patients (34.1%) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Comorbidities in patients with AKI not associated with COVID-19.

Of the patients with AKI not associated with SARS-CoV2 infection, 39% (17 patients) died. On the other hand, 27 patients (61%) received treatment and were subsequently discharged from the hospital (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Mortality among patients with AKI not associated with COVID-19.

Patients with AKI associated with COVID-19 infection had an alarming mortality rate, with only 1 patient (5%) out of 22 surviving. The remaining 21 patients (95%) did not survive. The primary cause of death was attributed to multiple organ dysfunction syndrome resulting from the COVID-19 infection (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Mortality among patients with AKI associated with COVID-19.

Conclusion

Advanced age is a significant risk factor for developing AKI due to associated comorbidities. The presence of underlying medical conditions renders the kidneys more susceptible to damage and the development of AKI. COVID-19 infection appears to target pre-existing kidney damage, particularly in patients with diabetes or arterial hypertension. Given the high mortality associated with AKI linked to COVID-19 infection in elderly patients, it is essential to carefully monitor biochemical markers of renal function and promptly initiate hemodialysis if necessary.

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